

СОФИЙСКИ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ „СВ. КЛИМЕНТ ОХРИДСКИ”

Информационен резонанс на книгата „Such a Fun Age” от Кайли Рийд

Информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ
(2019-2023)

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Дата: 09.06.2023 г.

Увод

Обект на настоящото проучване е книгата „Such a Fun Age” на Кайли Рийд. Мотивите за избор на обекта са високите очаквания на нейните издатели и противоречивите коментари, отзиви и критики за нея, след като беше публикувана и разпространена в книготърговските мрежи.

Целта на настоящото проучване е да открие, представи и обобщи всички форми на информационен резонанс на книгата „Such a Fun Age ” и на база тази обратна връзка да се провери хипотезата, че книгата се е осъществила като медия.

Задачите на проучването включват намиране и представяне на различните форми на обратна връзка с автора относно книгата във всяка от осемте фази на

алгоритъма за информационно търсене на информационен резонанс на книга, обобщаване и визуализиране на данните чрез диаграми, рекапитулация на резултатите чрез количествено обобщение и да се направи извод, като се отговори на въпроса дали книгата се е осъществила като медия.

Методиката на работа, която ще бъде използвана в настоящето проучване, включва информационно търсене, информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ. За извършването на библиометричния анализ ще бъде използван инструментът „Алгоритъм за информационно търсене на информационния резонанс на книга в 8 фази”, разработен от М. Цветкова.¹

Обхватът на проучването включва пълното издание на книгата. Информационният мониторинг включва всички български и чуждестранни канали, които могат да дадат информационен резонанс на книгата. Няма ограничения в езика. Изследването обхваща периода от 2019 г. до 2023 г.

Обект на изследването (английски оригинал):

Author:	Kiley Reid
Title:	Such a Fun Age
Publisher:	G. P. Putnam's Sons
Edition/Format:	Print book: Fiction
Subjects:	Adult -- Fiction. Race-- Fiction.
Genre/Form:	Fiction Contemporary
Document Type:	Book
All Authors / Contributors:	Kiley Reid
ISBN:	9781526612144, 1526612143
OCLC Number:	1153974787
Description	310 pages

¹ Tsvetkova, Milena. Reading as Communication Echo: Scientific Model of the Reader's Feedback Research. Saarbrücken, Germany: Lambert Academic Publishing, 2017. 120 p. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3204060>

Изобр.1. Корица на книгата „Such a Fun Age” (2019)²

Информационно-резонансното (медийно-рефлексивното) поле на книгата „Such a Fun Age“ - реакциите на читателите ѝ във вид на обратна връзка, ще бъде проследено чрез информационен мониторинг по 8 основни фази:

- I. Симултанни онлайн практики и директна обратна връзка с автора;
- II. Номинална (формална) обработка - библиографско описание, преиздание;
- III. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието - класифициране, предметизиране (извеждане на ключови думи); анонси, анотации, резюме, реферат; съкратени версии на книгата;
- IV. Репродукция (деривация) - цитиране, перифразиране, ремиксиране, фен творчество (фенфикшън), преводи;
- V. Текуща (оперативна) критика - ревю (преглед); търговски и читателски класации;
- VI. Експертна (научна) критика - професионални награди; изследвания и интерпретации;

² Such a Fun Age [photo]. In: Amazon, 31.12.2019 [cited 07.06.2023]. Available from: <https://www.amazon.com/Such-Fun-Age-Kiley-Reid/dp/052554190X>

VII. Медиаморфози (медийни репрезентации, продължения, трансакции, транскодиране, трансмутации, конвертиране на книгата в друг медийен формат) - екранизиране на книгата, поставяне на сцена като театрална постановка и други практики, форми и изкуства, появили се в следствие на прочита на книгата;

VIII. Историзация (меморизация и митологизация).

Фаза 1. Симултани онлайн практики и директна обратна връзка с автора

В тази фаза ще бъдат отразени коментари в социалните мрежи Goodreads и Library Thing. Ще бъдат търсени и представени само коментари с текст без ограничение в езика, както и примери за директна обратна връзка с автора. Ще бъдат търсени и коментари в български онлайн книжарници (ozone.bg; helikon.bg; hermesbooks.bg; ciela.com; knizhen-pazar.net).

Коментари в Goodreads:

Such a Fun Age. In: Goodreads, 2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/43923951-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Най-стари:

“Immediately immersive; Emira loves babysitting Briar, but feels at 25 her life should be more developed, like her friends are. Alix, Briar's mom, adores Emira a bit too much, while spending her time justifying why her life is as amazing as it used to be~ they're both flawed yet relatable characters!

The story tackles race, how we identify with each other and ourselves. I loved the story's approachable, chaotic, and honestly fun voice~ just what I was looking for!

Galley borrowed from the publisher. “; Jillian Doherty. - In: Goodreads, 11.02.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2711587164> [05.06.2023]

“This is a fantastic new addition to the literary fiction shelf.

The story follows two women during two very different stages of life, yet also not too far apart in age. Emira is about to turn twenty-five and desperately needs a job with benefits. However, she can't let go of her babysitting job with the delightful and lovable Briar Chamberlain. The story also follows Briar's mom, Alix, who is a self-made woman, building up her brand and career with supportive family and friends behind her. Their lives of comfortable routine get mixed up after a racially-charged incident in a grocery store involving Emira and Briar. Their stories then progress in an attempt to cope with the situation in their own unique ways.

The story is so much more than the plot though. Kiley Reid brilliantly brings a fictional setting that feels so close to the real world, you almost feel like you know a Emira or an Alix. The characters feel so genuine and see their reality as general truth, which is so relatable to how people interact with each other today.

What really blew my mind, as a POC, is how well Reid captured the way some people try to overcompensate with their friendships with people of different races. It's such a small thing, but can really effect friendships, families, and daily life.

If you like literary fiction that tackles on current issues and makes you think about your relationships with the people around you, then pick this book up.

Read thanks to an ARC from Putnam.”; Virginia. - In: Goodreads, 23.04.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2782692782> [05.06.2023]

“In an era of so many white savior narratives, it’s so refreshing to see a story written by a black woman that directly challenges and upends that problematic narrative trope.

Alix Chamberlain is the textbook well-meaning rich white woman: She has black friends. She’s read everything Toni Morrison wrote. She’s trying to land a gig with Hillary Clinton’s campaign.

Emira Tucker is the 25-year-old black woman who babysits Alix’s two young daughters. She’s aimlessly trying to figure out her life—preferably before she turns 26 and loses her parents’ health insurance.

One night when Emira is at a grocery store with Alix’s daughter, she’s confronted by a security guard who accuses her of kidnapping the young girl. A white man named Kelley films the incident, and he and Emira begin dating.

Horrified that this happened to Emira, Alix resolves to make things right, but as it turns out, Kelley is someone from Alix’s past, and things start to get messy.

While the central conflict of the narrative rests on a premise that is perhaps unrealistically coincidental, the fact remains that this book is compulsively readable. The characters are so well-developed and the dialogue so authentic, with tons of little details and observations.

Emira becomes the reluctant target of both Alix and Kelley’s well-intentioned but problematic white saviorism, as they both try to do what they believe is best for her, pushing her life in what they perceive to be the right direction. But Emira doesn’t need to be saved—especially not by these two.

Laced with important commentary about race and privilege, this is ultimately a story about owning one’s own life. Emira may be the aimless one, but she’s true to herself—something that, we come to find, isn’t the case for Alix, despite how much she seems to have it all together.

I really enjoyed this and never wanted to put it down while I was reading it. I have no doubt that it’ll get a ton of buzz when it comes out.

Thanks to NetGalley for a free advanced copy in exchange for an honest review.”; Jessica Sullivan. - In: Goodreads, 15.05.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2813583568> [05.06.2023]

“Wow. What did I just read? Such a Fun Age starts with a babysitter being accused of kidnapping the little girl she is watching but quickly takes the reader in several different directions. Race, privilege, long-held grudges, and some seriously deranged main characters are masterfully woven through this gripping story that left me emotionally cringing. Kiley Reid is a fresh voice in fiction and obviously an author that we will want to see so much more from! I am solidly one of her biggest fans.”; Mary. - In: Goodreads, 17.05.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2824449731> [06.06.2023]

“Dang, I don't know what about this was so good, but I read it in one sitting! Some powerful questions of race and class dynamics; very realistic dialogue; an adorable toddler asking adorable toddler questions (“Why don't we know that lady?” “Where's that doggy's mom?”). A refreshing change to have the babysitter's charge actually be its own character, rather than just set decoration! This is like if “The Nanny Diaries” were actually a serious book dealing with tough issues, rather than a popcorn read.”; Tory. - In: Goodreads, 05.05.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2833837656> [06.06.2023]

“SUCH A FUN AGE is absolutely brilliant. Kiley Reid has a beautiful way of writing about absolutely terrible every day horrors in a way that is almost too easy to read. She explores both sides of a working relationship. Alix is a white, upper class woman who hires Emira, a 25-year old black woman, to work as a babysitter for her son. After Emira is accused of kidnapping Alix's son one night at a grocery store, events unfold that show the ways in which casual racism permeates the world. I finished this book with a smile and was immediately hit with a wave of “oh man the world is a truly horrible place.” Reid has created amazing, three-dimensional characters that make you feel for all of them, causing me to change loyalties with each chapter. This book deserves all of the attention it is getting.”; Portia. - In: Goodreads, 31.05.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2839770333> [06.06.2023]

“This book will keep you up way past your bedtime just to see how things will turn out. Full of nuanced characters and a very current plot, Such a Fun Age will keep

you slightly off-balance and questioning how you would react. Emira is a character that you'll love for her feistiness and strength of character.”; Linda Quinn. - In: Goodreads, 01.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2840104346> [06.06.2023]

“a phenom debut, full of complicated characters who all share fault and all look like people you and I might actually know. I was grabbed by the opening, but then I ~really~ fell into it with a perfectly placed jaw-dropper of a closing line at the end of part one and I decided to blow off my Friday evening plans just to read more.

superb stuff; 2020 is going to be a great year for books.”; Drew. - In: Goodreads, 02.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2814508065> [06.06.2023]

“I tore through this book. Definitely a must read when it comes out - important and extremely relevant in the face of so much white saviorism in popular culture.”; Shira Selkovits - In: Goodreads, 02.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2817592240> [06.06.2023]

“This novel is a reflection of current issues told in a refreshing voice. Emira is a babysitter for a well-meaning rich family that has started to treat her more like family than staff after an unexpected event happens at their home. Emira loves her job and while all her friends are managing to move into the career world, she knows she is good at being a nanny and can't really see herself doing anything else; that is until a video is leaked, and the true indentations of her employer come to light.

A razor-sharp, unforgiving and unforgettable debut that had me from the opening lines.”; Shannon A. - In: Goodreads, 03.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2845613081> [06.06.2023]

“This is such a fun, gossipy read despite the subject matter that is quite serious. I received an Advance copy of this at BookExpo, and it was the one book that I packed in my bag to take with me instead of shipping home with my other ARCs. It immediately pulled me in, and I read it desperately over my breakfasts and on my lunch breaks at work because I just had to know what would happen next. Each character is distinct and has their own voice, Briar is completely charming, believable, and lovable, and everyone has realistic flaws that made me cringe while also somehow pulling me deeper into the story.

Reading this book was like having a good gossip session with your best friend, one in which you both acknowledge your own short comings and biases while skewering other people's at the same time. There were so many moments in the book when the narrator would point out something about the little tics of behavior that white people have around POC (like when Emira mentions walking into an office of white women, who all treat her with extra-exaggerated courtesy because of her skin color, as if to prove they aren't racist) that made me go "oh, crap, I totally

unconsciously do that, and I never realized it was that obvious.” At the BookExpo book buzz panel the editor mentioned that the author said there were no heroes in this book, that every character had flaws, and that she wanted everyone to feel just a little bit called out. She managed to do that, while also making it somehow so damn fun to read.”; Caitlin. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2843433993> [06.06.2023]

“Great debut! A young black babysitter gets caught up in a moment when she’s stopped by a security guard at a grocery store while taking care of her white charge. In the age of on-demand videotaping on devices, her moment was magnified and threatens to unleash all sorts of past grudges and misplaced intentions. Electrifying and layered, this book is timely and discussible. Perfect for book clubs and for fans of Laura Sims and Liane Moriarty.

Thanks to the publisher for an advanced copy.”; Mrs C. - In: Goodreads, 06.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2849173499> [06.06.2023]

“Having babysat in NYC for 10+ years, there is so much in this book I can relate to. Regardless of your background and ethnicity, I think many women are going to be able to relate to Emira’s journey in this book. I am so impressed with Kiley Reid’s ability to tackle the huge topic of race in such a humorous and upbeat tone.

I received an early copy of this book through the publisher at Book Expo.”; Allyson. - In: Goodreads, 10.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2845067411> [06.06.2023]

“A masterful exploration of character that explodes the white savior narrative. You’re going to want to read everything Kiley Reid has ever written.”; Heather. - In: Goodreads, 15.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2859255933> [06.06.2023]

“So goddamn smart and nuanced and empathetic and also FUN!!! The dialogue is phenomenal, the characters are 100% real people that I now know. The author has so much empathy for all of them without letting any of them off the hook. An absolute pleasure to read while giving me so much to think about.”; Kelsey. - In: Goodreads, 17.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2858189785> [06.06.2023]

“Well this is propulsive. This book gets in and out with a snappiness that is delightful. Kiley Reid explores issues of race and youth so deftly while still writing a story that is a STORY - like there’s movement to the plot here that I wasn’t expecting. Reid drops bombs on you on page 75 and pays them off on page 100 (guessing at page numbers here) - instead of dragging you along for the entirety of the book, she doesn’t mess around with keeping the story moving. Things don’t stay secret in service of tension - the tension is BECAUSE the secrets are let out. I loved and hated all of these

characters in equal measure. Emira is ostensibly the protagonist, but Alix is not given a villain edit. My favorite thing, though, is how nothing is completely black or white - no one is completely in the wrong, and no one is completely right. For instance, white Kelley is shown to date black women almost exclusively, and while that could be a fetish it's also shown that he genuinely cares about Emira. The verdict on him is left up to the reader and I adore that.”; Jamie. - In: Goodreads, 19.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2863893706> [06.06.2023]

“I really liked this! The dialogue, in particular, is so well done (the 3 year old is just perfect) and the criticisms of whiteness feel really sharp - these dumb white people who are so wrapped up in worrying about race that they can't see Emira for a unique person. The economics realities of being a childcare worker are pretty accurate too, although I got super mad that she was working for them 20+ hours a week on a regular schedule and they were still calling her a babysitter and not a nanny. I do think Emira herself is just a little too good; I think the book tries to paint her lack of ambition as a flaw but doesn't really believe it, so doesn't convey that to the reader, either.

Still, lots to talk about, a great pick for book groups & fans of Celeste Ng's. Would not be at ALL surprised if Reese Witherspoon picks this for her book group.”; Emily. - In: Goodreads, 20.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2862828238> [06.06.2023]

“I absolutely loved this book. You don't often see the complexities of race, class, and gender coming together so well like this - no preaching, just real life as it is lived, with all its baffling contradictions and unexpected twists and turns. You never feel anything is forced, unlike so many self-conscious "PC" writers of today, who carry their points home with a sledgehammer. Like a well-written mystery novel, little hints and clues to a character's personality are dropped everywhere until they come together in the end.

The only thing that annoyed me was the condescending endorsement the publisher chose to use on the back of the book. The quote reads: "Kiley Reid is the author we NEED now." It sounds like a phrase Alix might have uttered. Why "need"? We've always "needed" great writing and good stories. Instead of saying how great her writing is or how unique her story is, the quote implies that she is "needed" because of her race (as if she fills some quota). Yes, we "need" authors like Kiley Reid because the book industry doesn't have enough nonwhite voices, but what about her gifts as a writer? Would anyone have said the same of Stephen King: "King is the author we NEED now" ?

Ignore the wrongheaded endorsements and just plunge in. I wish more authors wrote like Kiley Reid. This is one author whose name I'll be on the watch for.”; Kelley. - In: Goodreads, 26.06.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2872882824> [06.06.2023]

“smart, addictive, excellently plotted.”; Kerry Cullen. - In: Goodreads, 02.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2878708637> [06.06.2023]

“Entertaining mostly towards the end. For a debut novel it wasn’t terrible, but I most definitely felt like I was reading a book written about black struggles by a white woman. The dialogue was also fucking atrocious.”; Asia J. - In: Goodreads, 03.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2873215432> [06.06.2023]

“Holy crumbs, I loved this book. It first came onto my radar when I read that Lena Waithe had optioned it (!). It’s pitch perfect.”; Courtney Gillette. - In: Goodreads, 04.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2512153114> [06.06.2023]

“Finally, a white savior novel that includes a fully developed perspective from the African American savior. Emira, the young black babysitter, is accused of kidnapping her charge and the entire incident is captured on video. After the incident, her employer, Alix, desperately wants to make it up to her and to become friends. Not only does the book explore race, class, privilege and turn all tropes on their heads, it brings back the reality that being in your 20s is hard and it really isn’t a fun age. How our past can haunt and shape us into the people we will be or become. This book is so relatable and readable that I suspect it will be a big hit when it enters the world in 2020.

I received an arc from the publisher but all opinions are my own.”; Audrey. - In: Goodreads, 04.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2881318955> [06.06.2023]

“first I’d like to get out of the way, that I highly recommend this book. It’s a page turner from the very beginning and a highly addictive read (like gossip) I did wish the end could have been different (for selfish reasons)”; Arnetra. - In: Goodreads, 06.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2886036789> [06.06.2023]

“3.5 rounded up

This book has been seriously hyped, and going in I was unsure of what to expect beyond an examination of the relationship between a young black woman and her affluent white employer. Fortunately *Such a Fun Age* is so much more than that.

Kiley Reid’s novel kicks off with Emira, a 25-year-old black woman who works part-time as a babysitter for Alix Chamberlain’s daughter Briar embarking on a late night visit to a supermarket Emira is involved in an altercation with a security guard who believes she has kidnapped Briar. While Emira is a little shaken by the incident

and looking to shrug it off Alix is outraged and wants to put things right. The incident is captured on video by a young (white) man who soon becomes a key part of the narrative too.

Emira is like many young women these days - muddling through her mid-20s without a whole lot of direction, feeling like her friends are all more successful and in a better place in life than she is. She is soon to turn 26 and therefore will no longer be covered by her parents health insurance, so is desperately looking for a job with this benefit (side note: I had no idea how much of a serious issue this was in America..). This search proves unsuccessful, and due to the nature of Alix's job (as an inspirational speaker) she needs Emira to work more hours, but she also wants to be Emira's friend and help her better herself. This is where things become problematic but thought-provoking: Alix is a typical "white saviour". You know the kind - she has black friends so how can she be racist, right?! This differs from other books of this ilk, however, as we have a highly developed African American protagonist who we view Alix's actions through, and the consequences of these actions and how this causes Emira to reassess her job.

This topic, along with the issues brought up around it (such as the transactional relationship of a nanny) for a stimulating topic to base a novel around. I would just add that despite the complex themes this is SO readable and I found it hard to put down. Recommended!

Thank you Netgalley and Bloomsbury Publishing for the advance copy, which was provided in exchange for an honest review.”; Sarah. - In: Goodreads, 09.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2830017224> [06.06.2023]

“Wonderfully written with excellent characterisation. You know a book is good when you find yourself thinking about the characters while you’re at work!

Many thanks to NetGalley for the ARC.”; Donna-Marie. - In: Goodreads, 11.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2891559092> [06.06.2023]

“Quick, interesting, fresh perspective. Well developed characters showed multiple perspectives, which were not overblown or caricatures. This is certainly going to stick with me for a while. Recommended!”; Cady. - In: Goodreads, 11.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2854700775> [06.06.2023]

“This book should and will rightfully be HUGE when it comes out in early 2020 (it is already going to be a movie or TV show made by the great Lena Waithe). Sharp and suspenseful (even though it’s not a mystery) - you don’t know how it’s all going to turn out, and there are no clear, easy answers about how it should. Truly fantastic to

read a buzzy, worthy of the hype novel about nanny-ing and bougie parents, and racial dynamics, written by a black woman.”; Michelle Ruiz Andrews. - In: Goodreads, 16.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2702895861> [06.06.2023]

“Sharp, quick writing gives way to ultra-relevant topics in this contemporary, realistic novel. The story is fun without being frivolous and so candid when bringing up real concerns like health insurance, it was refreshing. It was also great to see topics like interracial relationships, underemployment, and socioeconomic status covered with frank storytelling. Loved this one, can't wait to recommend it to young adult readers looking for themselves in stories.”; Andrea O. - In: Goodreads, 18.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2901039245> [06.06.2023]

“What a brilliant read! So well written and with characters that appear fully formed from the outset, ‘Such a Fun Age’ is the perfect family-centred novel for our times. Focusing on the fraught-with-difficulties relationship between the parent and child carer, Kiley Reid also explores race, self-conscious liberalism and economic hardship as she tells the story of Emira, her employee Alix and their daughter Briar.

Alix is an anxious person. Successful in her own right, she is still desperate for approval. Like many in this social media conscious age, she is forever wondering what her lifestyle choices look like to all around her. Is she liberal enough for her friends? Do they approve of her parenting choices? Can she even remember who she really is deep down? Kiley Reid contrasts her with babysitter Emira who wishes that race didn't have to be such an overriding issue in her relationship with Alix. She neither needs nor asks for Alix's friendship, finding the latter's courting of her perplexing and, at times, irritating. Whilst Emira is a great babysitter who genuinely cares for Briar, sadly that doesn't appear to be Alix's main concern.

This novel challenges us to think seriously about our own attitudes to race and class. It is an important read whilst also being extremely funny in part. Kiley Reid shows us clearly just how tediously self-referential white middle class liberalism can be. I loved Emira's response both to her employer's overtures and to the liberties that Alix takes. And what brave decisions she takes in the novel's final pages. You go, girl!

My thanks to NetGalley and G.P. Putnam's Sons for a copy of this novel in exchange for a fair review.”; Sarah. - In: Goodreads, 22.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2906178668> [06.06.2023]

“A bit uneven, especially at the beginning, but the pacing tightness up as the novel progresses. The book does a really nice job of showing how different characters see themselves and how others see them, and the gulf that exists between those perceptions, something I'm very into these days (see The New Me...). Reid has a keen eye for the people who inhabit different types of liberal whiteness and the ways they

construct themselves in relation to blackness, and a particularly incisive look at how well those folks can recognize hypocrisy in others and not themselves.”; Sydney. - In: Goodreads, 22.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2907120757> [06.06.2023]

“** spoiler alert ** Not really a big fan of the characters and their choices but mad props to Emira for being mature about the video ever since the grocery store incident.”; Meghan. - In: Goodreads, 22.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2862688921> [06.06.2023]

“I am loving all of the nanny books that keep coming lately. Working for a family is a very interesting dynamic; you are “part of the family”, but need to maintain professionalism. You are familiar, but not TOO familiar. I see why writers are exploring it more - it can get complicated. I am currently working as a nanny and have been with the family for 2 years now. I could relate so strongly to Emira’s feelings of being torn away from and drawn to her job.

This is a very powerful debut that touches on a lot of complex and touching issues, like ambition, race and class. I found this to be a very moving story.”; Annie. - In: Goodreads, 23.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2889810380> [06.06.2023]

“An excellent story about what it is like being a coloured person in a middle-class white culture.

It is a coming of age story but the person it concerns, Emira, comes of age much later than many.

Emira struggles to find a purpose and what she is really interested in - apart from dancing and drinking and going out - her teenage and college life never seems to end even though she has got her degree. Alex tries to help her, but fails to understand her and her background. And then we have a strange man - helping Emira - or not?

I found it difficult at times to understand the speech that the girls shared as it was very particular to their culture but mostly got the gist - I think.

It is tricky to think about your domestic help and what they might want from life - especially when they come from such a different culture to you. and when your immediate impulse is to help them find their way.

Truthfully we had a mother’s help with a degree and we did help her find her next job - after 2 years with us as we taught business skills and she helped with our own business as well as the children, and she came from a nice middle class white family so i have not been confronted with his dilemma personally. But I suspect I

would be an Alex!”; Jennifer Margeson. - In: Goodreads, 23.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2907846468> [06.06.2023]

““Such a Fun Age” is the smart and refreshing novel from a black writer that the world needed yesterday. Kiley Reid’s writing is beautiful, incorporating dialogue that is so incredibly real with characters that you’ll feel like you instantly know. This is a gossipy novel that tackles and directly challenges race and privilege and is absolutely a must-read.”; Amanda Zirn Hudson. - In: Goodreads, 24.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2864050922> [06.06.2023]

“An exciting, and wildly addictive, first novel. After a horrible mixup at a grocery store, the story tells such an interesting, sardonic and tough tale of race in modern Philadelphia. Always a thrill when you find a new writer who you know you’re going to look forward to for years to come.”; James B. - In: Goodreads, 24.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2850221629> [06.06.2023]

“Holy shit. Everyone needs to read this book.”; Claudia. - In: Goodreads, 26.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2912450763> [06.06.2023]

“Such a Fun Ages chronicles the happenings for Emira, a young babysitter, and the family she looks after directly following an altercation at a supermarket, where Emira is accused of kidnapping the young girl she is looking after.

I loved this book from start to finish! What a gem! What an interesting concept for a book, first off. Being Australian I was very interested to read about dynamics in America. I loved the characters - Emira was such a delight, and young Briar was hilarious. I loved her spirit. I enjoyed reading about Emira’s friends and their dynamics, and I thought Alix was a well drawn character who has a lot of conflicting aspects of her personality.

Loved it and will recommend.”; Sarah. - In: Goodreads, 28.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2914916184> [06.06.2023]

Enjoyed this one. No simple heroes or villains. Although the central coincidence is a little hard to swallow, the rest of the story rings true.”; Tracy Miller. - In: Goodreads, 29.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2916165815> [06.06.2023]

“The characterization in this book is amazing. Emira is in that stage between college and adulthood. Her friends are getting jobs and promotions, and she's still babysitting. Everyone is telling her to be more ambitious, to be someone she's not. Alix is so driven, she can be oblivious to everyone around her. I started out relating to her struggles balancing work and family. But as she starts to "help" Emira, her behavior becomes more and more appalling. Even 3-year-old Briar, with her love of teabags and endless questions, feels like a real person.

Received an advance copy from #netgalley.”; Sarah K. - In: Goodreads, 31.07.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2912913103> [06.06.2023]

“Fuck yeah!!!

Emira triumphs in the end, with her friends, and I love that. Like Emira I’m a little sad about one thing and one thing only. I hate to reveal too much about books before they’re published....

Sort of reminded me Queenie if Queenie wasn’t so messed up - due to their struggle to find themselves, both dated white guys of questionable intent, both had an incredible group of ride-or-die friends.

I expected to read a chapter and give it up. Instead I read the whole book in one night. The last two chapters just clinched it for me. So, so good.”; Ilyssa Wesche. - In: Goodreads, 01.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2920644677> [06.06.2023]

“A really interesting, well written story that looks at both subtle and not so subtle racism and the problem with “well-meaning” white people. Would definitely recommend. Educational (especially as a white woman reading) in a subtle way as well, given that it’s a fictional story, so it doesn’t read like a textbook or lecture.”; Haleigh K. 03.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2922575937> [06.06.2023]

“Phenomenal, absolutely phenomenal. Everyone please read this when it comes out!”; Rachel. - In: Goodreads, 05.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2915607568> [06.06.2023]

“This is fast-paced, highly enjoyable easy-reading fiction but with real depth. Emira is a great character; nuanced, unique, and utterly true to herself.”; Amy Rhodes. - In: Goodreads, 05.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2925398929> [06.06.2023]

“Alix Chamberlain is a white, successful Manhattan mom with two kids, a loving husband, and an amazing babysitter her daughter adores. She started as a blogger and has built her business showing other women how to get what they want.

Emira is a young black woman, a recent-ish grad feeling aimless in her next step in life, so she babysits 2 year old Briar while she tries to figure things out. She obviously loves being Briar’s caretaker, and their relationship is more than cute--it’s a once in a lifetime sort of thing. The two of them will steal your heart.

One night, when Emira is out late with the toddler, a security guard accuses Emira of kidnapping the child. The whole scene is caught on video, by a well-meaning white man named Kelley that Emira soon begins dating. Kelley coaxes Emira to post

the video, but she wants nothing to do with that or being the center of attention. Alix is mortified for Emira and wants rescue her from her situation, as does Emira's new boyfriend. Emira finds herself conflicted and unsure of what she wants, when someone from Alix's past upsets all of their lives.

The quick pace and tender heart of the story felt like watching a binge-able Netflix show like *Workin's Moms* or HBO's *Insecure*— slice-of-life stories from multiple perspectives. Complexities of racism, privilege, income gap, and gender roles that affect Alix and Emira makes this a reflective and meaningful book. An enjoyable and authentic page-turner great for the beach or train, but with nuanced and flawed characters that will make you ponder the idea of transactional relationships.

For fans of contemporary fiction, Celeste Ng, Tom Perotta, Issa Rae.”; LaRaie.
- In: Goodreads, 07.08.2019. Available from:
<https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2926999124> [06.06.2023]

“I want to thank Putnam for gifting me an ARC copy of this book at the United for Libraries Author Tea at ALA Annual 2019. I have not received any money from the publisher for this review.

Short Review

Kiley Reid is a fresh voice in fiction, and her debut novel *Such a Fun Age* critically examines and flips the “white-savior motif” through the character of Emira as well as her employer, Alix Chamberlain. The fact is there are a lot of incredibly selfish characters in this book, and the fact Emira couldn't see this is a bit problematic (I also felt like she didn't really have a lot of her own power in the decisions she made, a lot of it was based on what friends said or told her to do. I did want more from her, by the end she did make her own decisions but it felt rushed). This is an important read, but my main issues with this book is some pacing issues in the middle. I do think the themes are important and the writing is solid, and I'm interested to see what Kiley Reid will write next.”; Liz. - In: Goodreads, 11.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2883507345> [06.06.2023]

“I very much enjoyed this book.

Emira works as a sitter for Alix, taking care of her toddler daughter Briar. One night Emira is accused of stealing Briar and the story continues from there.

A real strength of this book is the depth of the characters. Each one was carefully written and each felt real and genuine. I loved the relationship Emira had

with Briar- relationships between all the characters were well managed and described.

I found this novel thought provoking and it made me think about how I would have reacted in different scenarios.

A great book by this talented author! Thank you to NetGalley and the publishers for my copy of this book.”; Tamsin Preece. - In: Goodreads, 13.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2935365176> [06.06.2023]

“This book explored race issues and identity in a way that I, as a white woman, never would have thought of. That, combined with the fact I could absolutely not put it down, made this an easy five-star read for me.

Thank you to Edelweiss and G.P. Putnam's Sons for providing me with a free review copy”; Tiffany. - In: Goodreads, 20.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2885643325> [06.06.2023]

“I loved this book so much!

Characters were spectacular. They were so complex and realistic. As soon as I thought I had one pegged, they took a left turn. Not in a manipulative sort of way, but in the best way, keeping me actively engaged throughout.

I will be pressing this into many hands!!”; Tricia Nociti. - In: Goodreads, 22.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2948223596> [06.06.2023]

“This debut novel juxtaposes race and class in an accessible, impactful way. Don't assume anything about these characters, because they are full of surprises. Reid's is a voice to watch!

This was an ARC from Book Expo, NYC, where I met Reid at an event. Her enthusiasm for storytelling is infectious, and Such A Fun Age is part of the conversation we need to be having in America right now.”; Tina Panik. - In: Goodreads, 25.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2948710876> [06.06.2023]

“Some deep shit happening here and a few complicated relationships making this an excellent debut novel.”; Donna Foster. - In: Goodreads, 25.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2931046604> [06.06.2023]

“This book is relatable and incisive and fascinating and nuanced and well-plotted and devastating and also hilarious and I CAN'T WAIT FOR Y'ALL TO READ IT”; Nerdette Podcast. - In: Goodreads, 27.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2944739138> [06.06.2023]

“The book I needed to break my rut! Fast-paced and funny and chock-full of unreliable characters.”; Susannah Goldstein. - In: Goodreads, 19.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2942353645> [06.06.2023]

“I liked this book, more than I had expected to. The interaction between the two main characters, a young babysitter and her employer is difficult for me to relate to, but I did enjoy the book.

i received an ARC from G P Putnam through Goodreads.”; Nancy Shepherd. - In: Goodreads, 29.08.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2931068218> [06.06.2023]

“Thank you to G.A. Putnam and Penguin Random House for the opportunity to read this in advance.”; Michelle. - In: Goodreads, 02.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2952069462> [06.06.2023]

“Nuanced, timely, important, COMPULSIVELY readable and absolutely unputdownable- I flew through this in 24 hours, but I'll be thinking of this one for much, much longer. Grateful to have had a chance to read an early copy of this one, and absolutely certain you will be seeing it EVERYWHERE (with good reason) in the months to come.”; Mary. - In: Goodreads, 02.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2915368149> [06.06.2023]

“4.5 stars

As soon as I read the synopsis, I knew it was my kind of book. I'm so happy that I won an ARC in a giveaway (thank you to Putnam Books).

The book starts with an incident where Emira, a twenty-something black babysitter, is accused of kidnapping the young white toddler she babysits. Then we get to see the aftermath of this event, and how it changes the relationship between Emira and her boss, Alix Chamberlain.

First of all, I really enjoyed this book. I found the tone and writing style very compelling and easy to digest. There's so much to unpack in this novel, as the author

provides a social commentary on race and class. I really admired the way that Reid tackled some heavy topics with nuance, while keeping a relatively light tone.

Alix is horrified by what happens to Emira and wants to make things right. She's well meaning and consults her friends, including her close black friend, Tamra, about the situation and for advice on how to befriend Emira. Alix is convinced that everything she does is in Emira's best interest.

Meanwhile, Emira is young, broke, and a bit aimless. I found that very relatable as I think a lot of us have been in Emira's position and some point or another. She's still trying to figure out who she is and what she wants to do with her life. There are two main white people in Emira's life, and for a while, you're trying to figure who really has Emira's best interests in mind and who's just using her.

There's also a discussion about the people that we invite into our personal lives. Can the transactional nature of Emira's and Alix's relationship (babysitter and boss) be overshadowed by something deeper and more personal?

I thought these characters were well developed. With Alix in particular, I feel like we all know people IRL with similar traits. I really liked Emira and enjoyed getting to hear her story. There are contradictions within these characters, which the author uses to demonstrate that not everything is black and white.

I did think that the middle of the book was a bit meandering, but it starts off really strong and the plot really picks up in the last third of the book as everything comes to a head. Also, it struck me as odd that Emira, as a twenty-something in the year 2015/2016, does not have any social media accounts. I found that a bit hard to believe.

I have so much more to say about this book, but I'm going to leave it here to avoid getting into spoilers. As I mentioned, there's a lot to unpack in this novel and I wish I could have done it as a buddy read so that I'd have someone to discuss it with (if you've read it, come talk to me!).

This book is out in December and I'd definitely recommend it. It felt very accessible and I think this is a book that people could read that would make them examine their own privilege a bit.

//

I really enjoyed this one! A proper review to come.”; Nnenna | scsreads. - In: Goodreads, 03.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2963399792> [06.06.2023]

“What if your babysitter is dating your high school ex-boyfriend?

What if your boss once dated your boyfriend?

This debut novel explores the intersecting lives of Alix (the mom-boss) and Emira (the babysitter).

Often hilarious, this novel delivers serious scenes that reckon with racism, motherhood, life purpose, and telling the truth. Releases in January 2020. Thanks to the publisher and NetGalley for an ARC. Full review to come.”; Karen K. - In: Goodreads, 04.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2965348230> [06.06.2023]

“Recommending for Library Reads - full review to come closer to pub date! Loved it!”; Jill. - In: Goodreads, 05.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2966618734> [06.06.2023]

“It’s hard to describe this book - right and wrong, race, finding your way. It’s very good.”; Alissa. - In: Goodreads, 08.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2970106694> [06.06.2023]

“This book had pacing problems, problems with scene transitions, cringy dialogue, and overly preachy about social issues. Not a fan. The only thing that I liked in the book was the little girl, Briar.

ARC obtained at 2019 ARSL conference.”; Jessica T. - In: Goodreads, 09.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2971072831> [06.06.2023]

“This book grabbed me from page one, and I couldn’t tear my eyes from it. I lost hours to this book, completely forgetting where I was or what I was doing. Reid is a master at building tension between characters, and revealing secrets exactly where and when they need to come out. Protagonist Emira is scraping together a living as a babysitter and a typist in Philadelphia. When her boss calls and asks if she can take their little girl, Briar, late at night, Emira leaves a party to do so - beckoned by the money and her desire to help Briar, whom she loves. Emira takes Briar to a store, but is quickly questioned by a security guard, who suspects that she is a kidnapper, not a babysitter - due to her brown skin and party look. The novel moves back and forth

between Emira's perspective and that of her boss, Alix Chamberlain, a rich white Instagram influencer. The deep and powerful conflict between them is the heart of the novel, and it moves in every sphere, from the micro- to the macro-level. Beyond being a powerful story, though, this is an important story, especially for white women like myself who need to experience being uncomfortable with race so we can do better.”; Cari. - In: Goodreads, 09.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2971118031> [06.06.2023]

“Unique and confrontational

Debut author Kiley Reid worked as a babysitter in New York for six years. Reid lives in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania and is a recent graduate of the Iowa Writers' Workshop where she was the recipient of the Truman Capote Fellowship. Her first novel *Such a Fun Age* is published by G.P. Putnam's Sons, an imprint of Penguin Random House LLC.

Such a Fun Age tells the story of Emira, who is a young black babysitter in New York, trying to make the best of her life. When she babysits little Briar, rich and white Alix's daughter, one evening, Emira gets confronted by a security guard at a supermarket, accusing her of kidnapping the white child. Kelley records the whole incident with his phone and tells Emira to go to court over it, but Emira does not want any of that, all she want to do is live her simple life. But, after the incident, that simple life gets more complicated every day.

Reid takes the reader right into the action with the scene of Emira being accused, out late with Briar, of kidnapping the child and that's where this novel starts off. It is confronting and at the same time very recognizable. The racism in the very first chapter draws the reader right into the story and Emira's life. Although it seems very American to have a man coming up to Emira to tell her she has to put charges so she can get the guard fired or have a year's worth of groceries, the fact that lots of incidents and racist activities are going viral and everything and everyone is being watched is very universal nowadays.

“The more it was shared, the lighter it seemed to be, which made the whole thing both better and worse. Emira believed this light take was the consensus because of a few factors. First of all, no one got hurt. [...] This was a video about racism that you could watch without seeing any blood or ruining the rest of your day.”

Reid does not only show us racism in all kinds of ways, but she also successfully shows us the other side of the medal. Kelley is trying to prove he's not racist because of all his black friends and black girlfriends, but it so over the top it actually makes things worse. At the same time, the perfect, rich, but fake Alix may look like an angel but hires black babysitters all the same. Even the best intentions can lead to uncomfortable situations and Reid know how to capture them perfectly.

“It completely fetishizes black people in a terrible way,” Tamra went on. “It makes it seem like we're all the same, as if we can't contain multitudes of personalities and traits and differences. And people like to think that it says something good about them, that they're so brave and unique that they would even dare to date black women. Like they're some kind of martyr.”

But Such a Fun Age is more than a book about racism, race and privilege. In many ways the story is very recognizable for the many situations that are characteristic to our current society. The reader gets more introduced in the different lives Alix and Emira lead after the first chapter and it really helps them understand how you sometimes can do the wrong thing for the right reasons, but also the right thing for the wrong reasons. Also, Reid shows that the perfect life Alix seems to have in comparison to Emira, isn't that perfect after all.

“Alix quickly responded, and then continued captioning future Instagram photos she'd taken in the city. She now had enough content for weeks to continue pretending that she still lived there.”

Reid's style is very easy to read and can be identified as the voice of a generation. Such a Fun Age is an unique and confrontational story. It is relevant, witty and smart, just as the cover promises and it is very much a story about this very moment, a timely debut novel that stands in the heart of today's world and at the same time is timeless in its themes.

- Many thanks to the publisher for making an ARC available for this review through Edelweiss+"; Anne. - In: Goodreads, 09.09.2019. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2872555395> [06.06.2023]

Най-нови

“Heel pakkend en vernieuwend boek!”; Eva. - In: Goodreads, 06.06.2023.
Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5546029278> [06.06.2023]

“Honestly a very tough read. Probably the book I least wanted to finish this year but ONLY because of how it challenged my thinking. I found myself relating to both Alix & Emira. Emira & I are the same age, similar in a lot of ways, but I am white. My experience in the world doesn’t involve as much defensive thinking. I relate to Alix in appearance, naivety of the world in terms of race (albeit not as naive as her but) & probably also upbringing (but def didn’t have a mansion with a gate code or a full time baby sitter (or even a part time babysitter HA)).

SPOILERS:

I loved how Emira came into who she was. She knew she had to leave Kelley & Mrs C (Alix) in order to be herself. She kept her friends, she became dedicated in her work & loyal to a boss who wanted her to succeed in her career more than she wanted E for an employee.

I read the last paragraph probably 5 times because it was so haunting. I have to be hopeful that Briar never changed who she was. That she kept loving fish & saying her first thoughts & being who Emira loved. I can’t think of her becoming entitled & self-serving as Alix.

When it’s revealed that Alix’s notes went in Robbie’s locker & not Kelley’s, Alix “chooses to continue to believe the narrative that serves her.” When I was reading that part, I wasn’t surprised but I was perturbed. But as I thought about it I realized that’s so easy to do. Although I haven’t believed a narrative that dramatic, life altering, & path driving, I very easily can say my driving fast is necessary while someone else’s is annoying & they need to learn to chill. I can say oh I’m acting like a B because my day has been awful & you’re acting like a B because that’s who you are. Even if I’m not going as far as Alix did, I’m still guilty of the same thing— however I’m willing to learn to spot those things in myself & hopefully change them for the better.

Talking about race & living in a world so defined by race is such a complicated & tricky matter. The human experience is wild in & of itself, without even getting into race. Bridging gaps between differences will always come with some grinding friction & it will probably always take a lot of intentionality to face. Hopefully we can learn from these characters as well as our every day lives.”; Ann Bradley M. - In:

Goodreads, 06.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5571958795> [06.06.2023]

“A book about race and privilege with the story of a babysitter and her employer. The story was drawn out for too long and there ended up being no character development so it was kinda frustrating. I’d say it was a quicker read and had entertaining dialogue but the ending felt like the characters were back where they started.

I expected more from a Reece’s book club pick.”; Elizabeth. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5598704470> [06.06.2023]

“I had higher expectations for this one. Alix / Alex was entirely unlikable and Emira was too weak.”; Rox. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3257004133> [06.06.2023]

“Almost edge of seat reading”; Laurie Addoms. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5598532265> [06.06.2023]

“Too much crude language for me.”; Amber. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5594068152> [06.06.2023]

“This book deserves 3.5 honestly. Did I enjoy this book kinda. It was a rollercoaster of emotion where you don’t know who to shake your head at more. I don’t know who is more delusional Alix or Kelly. These are two people who think they are right but are wrong but refuse to understand why. It was very eye opening and I would tell my friends to read but it didn’t really hit the meat and potatoes till like close to the end.”; Sharonda Byrd-Bradbury. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5448802292> [06.06.2023]

“2.5 - did not relate or connect to any characters”; Sukhjit. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5597710394> [06.06.2023]

“I still don’t trust Kelley Copeland. And let’s hear it for the Iowa Writer’s Workshop!!!!!!!!!!!!”; Lindsey. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/4147550865> [06.06.2023]

“While I found this story compulsive enough to finish in a few days, I found myself thinking that none of the characters felt real. Not that people similar to these characters dont exist in real life, but that these specific characters did not feel real to me. The author included plenty of details to attempt to convince me that them and the side characters were real, but I just wasn’t buying it.

It was kind of interesting to read an adult fiction book that deals with racism rather than a middle grade or YA novel. Even though this story literally revolved around race, it was refreshing to read something not didactic and blunt.”; Abbigail. - In: Goodreads, 05.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3372899304> [06.06.2023]

“Admittedly, I did not expect to enjoy this debut novel plot but it definitely consumed my thoughts several times and became an engaging read. This book doesn’t waste time with the fluffy details and prioritizes a central moral focus through a well balanced narrative that doesn’t heavily depend on an overzealous approach to incorporate intricate, complex concepts/elements for possible literary recognition. The author portrays an experienced, personable understanding of social constructs and genuine desire to incite a purposeful message”; Marissa. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5484780703> [06.06.2023]

“I can’t decide if this is 3.75? There were parts and story lines I didn’t like, characters that I thought were overly stereo-typed (for a book based on racial inequities, I found this odd) and others that made me cry. This isn’t a feel good book, and I thought it would be... although that was purely from the title (whoops). Poor Emira gets endlessly shit on and the Briar element was sad.”; Shay Radeaux. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5596862975> [06.06.2023]

“Not typically a book that I would reach for, but I enjoyed it nonetheless. I liked how this book explored the differences in relationships based on age, race, social and economic status. By telling the story from both the point of view of Emira and Alix, it showed how different two people can view the same situation.”; Ashlyn. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/5596852876> [06.06.2023]

“An authentic book about very deep topics such as privilege, both white and socioeconomic. The dual perspectives were intriguing rather than annoying as I’m not a huge dual perspective fan. And to finish it off, how realistic and captivating this book was, I couldn’t put it down because it was like watching my favorite movie.”; Elizabeth. - In: Goodreads, 04.06.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/4953016473> [06.06.2023]

Общият брой на отзивите за книгата „Such a Fun Age” в Goodreads е 476 020, като има 38 503 отзива с текст на различни езици. Най-много коментари има на английски език (36 259). Отзивите, които могат да бъдат проследени в уебсайта са най-старите и най-новите 300, като това включва както оценки, така и коментари с текст. Намерени са 84 коментара, от които 83 са на английски език и 1 на нидерландски език.

Коментари в LibraryThing

Английски език:

“Highly enjoyable. I'm a bit surprised this was long-listed for the Booker, since it's not what I consider a literary achievement. But as an engaging, contemporary read, you can't go wrong. Painfully accurate characters and those tiny moments of self-doubt and failed human interaction that torment anyone with a brain. And I'd be remiss if I didn't mention the character of Briar; how many three-year-olds emerge from a novel with a fully-rounded personality and most of the best lines?”; therebelprince. - In: LibraryThing, 01.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/239826040> [06.06.2023]

“what a book! a terrific debut by Kiley Reid! the characters were so well developed.. they were all so fascinating and refreshing and thought provoking. things were complicated from the beginning which gave it the biggest pull in and i couldn't stop reading. the complexities of the inner thoughts from each of the characters added so much realness and each character's inner voice was worth examining. i had to put my own judgements aside to really get each one of their points of view. we all had thoughts we were not proud of. should we beat ourselves up for our ugly thoughts or should we acknowledge them and let them pass? this book was sharp and warm humor funny. the story flows very well and this story is modern and relatable and makes you pause to think about the issues being explored/talked about. there are so many issues this novel explored.. race and interracial dating.. motherhood and female friendships and each was examined in a hilarious and thoughtful way. this was a great read that touched on a ton of important, relevant issues. it would be so easy to judge or point fingers at any one of the leading characters, but i think this novel provided an opportunity to get bigger than finger pointing.. instead it's worth looking at the bigger issues at hand and the humanity of the human condition. i hope Briar is okay!!”; Ellen-Simon. - In: LibraryThing, 06.04.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/238142418> [06.06.2023]

“I had this downloaded and it was one of those books I'd forgotten the premise of, but wanted to read because I remembered people had said it was good. Good things always come of that, right? Well, didn't realise I was going to be reading this at such a timely moment but oh I'm so glad I read it when I did.

Fantastically written. Light-hearted somehow, despite tackling a lot of microaggressions and really confronting the way people can act and think. Reid's characters were all so well-formed and I could relate to each of them enough to know how their actions would play out. And the way the narratives fell, wow. Thought-

provoking yet distracting and a quick read.”; whakaora. - In: LibraryThing, 05.03.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/236168307> [06.06.2023]

“Rather than go into details, I'll simply say this is another one that failed to engage the reader. Too much dialog, flat characters and a slow moving plot that lacked a theme. DNF!”; Jonathan5. - In: LibraryThing, 20.02.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/235370807> [06.06.2023]

“Such a Fun Age is a 2019 novel by American author Kiley Reid. It is her debut novel and tells the story of a young Black woman who is wrongly accused of kidnapping while babysitting a white child, and the events that follow the incident. When Emira is apprehended at a supermarket for 'kidnapping' the white child she's babysitting, it sets off an explosive chain of events. Her employer Alix, a feminist blogger with the best of intentions, resolves to make things right. But Emira herself is aimless, broke and wary of Alix's desire to help. When a surprising connection emerges between the two women, it sends them on a crash course that will upend everything they think they know about themselves, each other, and the messy dynamics of privilege.

At the start of the novel, I couldn't identify with the characters, but then things started to come out and became clearer in the eighth chapter. As I listened to it in audio, which helped me envision the story, and then it became more engaging. Such a Fun Age takes contemporary young adulthood as its subject with fast fashion, trap music (which I had to look up its meaning, [Trap is a subgenre of hip hop music that originated in the Southern United States during the late 1980s. The genre gets its name from the Atlanta slang word "trap", a house used exclusively to sell drugs.] and Lean In-style feminism. It explores race, class and white privilege. Is this novel a lesson for white liberals?

Emira lacks confidence in herself as she settles into her own life and jobs. Alix Chamberlain is a feminist white who writes letters to corporations for free products, jobs and works for the Hilary Clinton Foundation, and is obsessed with Emira, and her lifestyle. I didn't understand Alix's obsession to be friends with Emira.

My turnoffs in the book are 1) Emira's group of friends that only seem to be interested in drinking, partying and hanging out, a generational thing. Kelley Copeland's obsession with being around black athletes and rappers or black culture. 3) Alix's love of Emira. I loved the endearing relationship between Emira and Briar, the 4-year-old that she cared for. I was totally surprised by the direction the author

took me in. I liked the ending. I just watched a movie very reminiscent of this storyline called “Like Sunday, Like Rain.” Overall, the drama was there, the mystery and the social issues in which Reid wrote very well, descriptive, sometimes funny and all of that made this a worthwhile read.”; Onnaday. - In: LibraryThing, 01.02.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/230534950> [06.06.2023]

“I didn't love it. I thought certain aspects were good, like the depiction of white saviorism, for example. But for the most part, everything was just unbelievable and all of the characters were caricatures and the dialogue was so bad and it just didn't work. Disappointing :("”; ninagl. - In: LibraryThing, 07.01.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/232545974> [06.06.2023]

“This book is exceptionally plotted. However, a lot of things about it irked me. Emira is relatively powerless for a majority of the book, with life happening to her vs her taking charge, which however intentional didn't sit well with me. The dialogue of her and her friends, and read in the audiobook, made me uncomfortable, especially reading about how the author's upbringing was more like Alix's than Emira's – it felt like caricature. Why did her part of the narrative get the least amount of words? I also know many kids Briar's age, and they don't talk like Briar does, it seemed off.

Kelley and Alix are well fleshed out and, while not entirely relatable, are familiar enough to despise and, despite everything, even sometimes care about. But this makes me bummed out that Emira wasn't as developed.

The prose are very straightforward, and there are many descriptions that felt unnecessary to the point of being jarring. It's simple, mass market writing.

While we are supposed to think Alix is ridiculous in many ways, the constant conversations reiterating her weight, how much she had to lose, what she should eat, and her friends body-shaming her – it upset me and did not come across as making fun but as unnecessarily reinforcing unhealthy body standards. I understand the picture the author was illustrating about white affluent mothers and their obsessions, but it happened so many times – in addition to the narrative's obsession with Kelley's hand size that seemed, again, to be repeated a few too many times – that it turned me off a bit. So if you're like me, TW: ED. Another thing that I didn't quite get was regardless of the letter, Kelley messed up, violated her trust and invited all his guy friends over the night they first slept together. Who cares if he got the letter or not? It was messed up. Having a giant house doesn't mean people are allowed to trespass. It confused me that her finding them mattered at all. Also, bottom line: I cannot imagine caring this much about a high school ex. Does anyone after age 30? In any case, this book felt like it was written by an affluent person trying to capture the plight of young Black women, and nailed it in many ways but not without sacrificing authenticity.

Coming from a news background, fact-checking elements that I'm itching to point out:

Every news station has to get at least informal permission from the person who filmed the video. Ensuring that these permissions were legally secured used to be a large part my former job. They can get sued to high heaven if they don't attempt to. There's no case that I'm aware of of passing permission on to someone because you send it to their email and verbally relinquished ownership.

Because it shows an absurd amount of bias, basing a story around a newscaster's wife and within the newscaster's own home would most likely never get approval from station execs.”; ostbying. - In: LibraryThing, 01.01.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/232130909> [06.06.2023]

“Maybe I'm too old for the target audience or perhaps it's because I don't have children or maybe I look for some deeper characterization in my reads. This story of a black babysitter looking after a precocious young girl had promise but it fell flat for me.

Emira is hired by Alix, a lifestyles blogger who wants to write a book, to look after her two young children. Alix's husband is a TV broadcaster and after he pronounces an ad lib that many take as racist their house is targeted by protesters. They call Emira in to look after the girls and when Briar, the older daughter is upset by the baby's crying they ask Emira to take Briar to the local supermarket. There a security guard questions why Emira, a black woman, has a white child with her and she is arrested for kidnapping. Once the police contact the parents Emira is released but a male customer, Kelly, videos the encounter. When Kelly later sees Emira on the subway he asks her on a date. Things seem to be progressing nicely for Emira until Alix asks her to Thanksgiving dinner with her date, Kelly. As Alix opens the door to Emira and Kelly she realizes that he knew her in high school and they have a history. Both accuse the other of racist actions: Alix once called the police on some black kids who were hanging out in her back yard and Kelly always hung out with the black kids and Alix felt he fetishized them. Kelly wants Emira to leave Alix's employment and Alix wants Emira to break up with Kelly. The video Kelly made goes viral (due to Alix's interference) and Emira severs ties with both of them.

The best character was Briar who was handed some of the best lines in the book. I felt sorry that she lost Emira from her life because neither of her parents seem to have had any time for her.”; gypsismom. - In: LibraryThing, 05.12.2022.

Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/222121595>
[06.06.2023]

“If a book is able to evoke the spirit of agitation within me, then it's good to me. I really enjoyed this book. If I had a physical copy, I'm sure I would have thrown it across the room a couple of times. I will be re-reading for an in-depth and closer read.”; Jaleesa_RBTBC. - In: LibraryThing, 02.12.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/230402161> [06.06.2023]

“I will admit, I was mixed on this and almost quit it during the Thanksgiving scene, but I am glad I held out until the end because Reid brings it back home. This book deals with so many items around race that I almost missed them because I thought the Thanksgiving scene was too much. I keep using this term to describe a plot line which I don't want to spoil, but it culminated at this scene.

Back to race. How do rich white people, look at college aged African American women. The idea of the “white savior” rang throughout the book, not only from the main relationship, but with the boyfriend. How black women treat each other, especially when class is involved. What is racist, especially systemic racism? There are so many ways these items are dealt with in a Lile story about a babysitter trying to live her life. So many trying to live her life for her or being outraged on her behalf. It was great at the end, but get through the Thanksgiving storyline.”; Nerdyrev1. - In: LibraryThing, 23.11.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/229922213> [06.06.2023]

“This was a second read for me. The first was the eBook. I am so glad I re-read it in the audiobook as being able to hear the dialogue really put me into the story. It's hard for me to say that there are any clear good and bad guys in this story. There are clear thoughts of OH NO this person really needs to reevaluate, but even Amira who is “supposed” to be the wronged party has her own flaws. Is she far more likable and better intentioned than Alex and Kelly yes! But all three's nuanced humanity is really what drew me in for a second read-through. While an easy read it is one that will truly make you think about race, intention, and how others can see the same situation in a different light depending on their own perceptions, and life experiences.”; Vintage_B. - In: LibraryThing, 06.11.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/223935299> [06.06.2023]

“Emira is a twenty-five-year-old African American woman who works babysitting and typing jobs. She feels she should have more of an idea of what to do with her life, but she enjoys taking care of three-year-old Briar. Briar's mom, Alix, is a white social media personality who is in the process of writing a book. Kelley is a thirty-something white businessman who goes out with Emira and knew Alix in years

before. Both Alix and Kelley try to “help” Emira in ways that are manipulative, condescending, and self-aggrandizing.

The initial scene in this book is absolutely spot-on and, for me, the best part of the entire book. I can easily picture the situation. A white security guard becomes suspicious of a babysitter for racist reasons, and it almost gets out of hand. A customer takes a video, which we know will play a role somewhere down the line. The author also does a great job of crafting the relationship between Emira and Briar. It is touching and realistic.

I liked the premise of this book, depicting casual racism in the US. I did not care much for the melodrama. Though the characters are all supposedly mature adults, they act like juveniles. They continue to re-hash ancient history from high school. I think regular readers of contemporary fiction will appreciate it even more than I did.”; Castlelass. - In: LibraryThing, 30.10.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/228374544> [06.06.2023]

“Oof, this book was good! It captured the nuance of dynamics that I'm so familiar with (the strange, charged relationship of a family and their caretaker, being an emerging young professional without the competitive ambition of peers) and revealed those that I know from only one perspective (that of your average well-meaning white individual) through the lens of a delicately human protagonist. 5 years later, this book is as readable and relevant as the moment during which it was published.”; graceandbenji. - In: LibraryThing, 01.09.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/223995354> [06.06.2023]

“I was worried this book wouldn't live up to all the hype, but it definitely did! My heart was racing during multiple scenes throughout the novel. The story struck the perfect balance between cringey and fun. One of my favorite reads of the year for sure.”; SarahMac314. - In: LibraryThing, 12.08.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/222573527> [06.06.2023]

“Enjoyed the storyline and the characters but thought the ending was a little lacking but I can't put my finger on why. Would read more by this author though.”; thewestwing. - In: LibraryThing, 12.08.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/222528742> [06.06.2023]

“Such A Fun Age is layered with complexities and I wasn't prepared to read but was glad to see nonetheless. What I probably admire most about the book was its ability to get its provoking message across to its audience while maintaining a breezy quality in its writing. It was easy to read and none of the issues discussed ever felt heavy-handed. I'm excited to see what Kiley Ried writes next.”; DominiqueDavis. - In:

LibraryThing, 09.08.2022. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/222348797> [06.06.2023]

“Not a bookclub book but a gift for Mother’s Day. Enjoyed it even though it was subtly about racism and did explain more about one’s world and each perspective. Glad to have read it.”; PatLibrary123. - In: LibraryThing, 09.08.2022. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/222333092> [06.06.2023]

“I stayed up late and woke up early to read this. It is both searing and empathetic.”; ZannaZori. - In: LibraryThing, 03.08.2022. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/221962529> [06.06.2023]

“I had started this a few times and finally got to listen to a hefty chunk of the novel while driving somewhere. I was drawn in by how perceptive it was, and Emira’s character (Emira babysits children in what she considers a different world), and of course the racial and social commentary. I may have listened to about half of it before it expired at the library so my score is not particularly reliable.

Nicole Lewis narrates this well.”; Okies. - In: LibraryThing, 18.07.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/219495125> [06.06.2023]

“Three and a half stars. Rating because I don’t like unreliable narrators. Otherwise this would be a five. I totally get why she did it, though. This book is the final word in unreliable narrators. It is a skillfully done character study that knows its writing beats. Reading this was a fantastic experience. Each character was interesting to study and I developed strong opinions, only to have them shattered 99% of the time twenty pages later, as more facts and different POVs about something were uncovered. Children were used as plot points. I can’t stand them IRL, and dislike reading them in fiction, but this author made them matter. While I hated Kelley, ultimately, Alex is the villain of the piece.

She engages in hardcore stalking of her employee rather than getting to know her; and absolves herself of any blame or guilt of anything, unless it’s performative. Alex has been assigning blame instead of apologizing for a long, long time. She was super trashy new money in high school, and had poor judgment and no knowledge of class etiquette as a result. I’m not exactly blaming her for that. Kelley is her boyfriend and desperate to be popular. When a bunch of popular jocks with raging senses of entitlement over other people’s property show up to her family’s new house for a party without her knowledge or consent, but Kelley’s implied encouragement, Alex calls the cops. She has been raised to believe cops are good. Kelley’s friend Robbie is arrested and loses his scholarship. Kelley breaks up with Alex to maintain his

new social status. It's heartbreaking Robbie was arrested and lost his scholarship. Alex wanted a romantic milestone evening with her boyfriend and had no idea a party had been planned at her house.

Kelley ruins everything. He didn't call the guys or even talk them out of it at school. Robbie never said, "This note is yours. Have a good time." He thought, "She MUST share her house." Alex was embarrassed by her parents' conspicuous spending. Everyone made a variety of bad choices and blames one another into adulthood. Everyone in this book sucks except Emira and her friends. Alex tries to control Emira outside of work and sees her, at most, as a teenager. She's an adult, and maybe eight years younger. I enjoyed Emira's friendship with Zara, and laughed at certain things Zara did in the end. I'm glad I got to read this and I hope the author continues succeeding.”; iszevthere. - In: LibraryThing, 28.06.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/219485200> [06.06.2023]

“This is a great book that tackles a lot of unexpected issues and it was definitely a page turner for me. My only criticism is that the ending felt a little choppy.”; awesomejen2. - In: LibraryThing, 21.06.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23215367/reviews/219031926> [06.06.2023]

“I appreciate the racial subject of the story and it was nicely handled. The author did a wonderful job detailing Emira's difficulties as well as the friendships that supported her.

That being said, I did not like this book. Correction - I did not like some of the characters in this book. Alix and Kelley annoyed me to know end. I've never read a book where two characters were so self involved and truly felt the world revolved around them. They truly showed the worst of people.”; Micareads. - In: LibraryThing, 21.06.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/219029473> [06.06.2023]

“I had tried to read this previously and put it down. I had to make a last minute book club substitution, chose it and i was glad I did. Initially, I found it annoying and this time through, I enjoyed it on many levels. What at first seemed predictable, turned out to be wrong. If at first the main theme seems to be race, I believe it is actually class. Emira is a wonderful character and the moral center of the novel.”; ccayne. - In: LibraryThing, 15.06.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/218460202> [06.06.2023]

“Read for debut, woman author of color. This story really gives you a look at racism from the top down instead of the bottom up. The question being what happens when you do the right thing for the wrong reason. I liked it for that reason. The

author did a great job of showing how what looks like good can be racism. The book was also long listed for the Booker prize. I don't think it was Booker quality but it was a good debut novel about an issue that is relevant.”; Kristelh. - In: LibraryThing, 24.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/215638022> [06.06.2023]

“This book was so uncomfortable in the best way.”; munchie13. - In: LibraryThing, 12.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/215342452> [06.06.2023]

“What an exceptional book this was. Convincing, moving, laugh out loud funny and thoughtful. It engaged me completely right from the start and kept me entertained to the last page. It's packed with believable characters and has a lot to say about human relationships and race. I loved it and am convinced that every book needs a Briar.”; whatmeworry. - In: LibraryThing, 09.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/215235238> [06.06.2023]

Немски език:

“Dieses Buch hat mich ein wenig irritiert - Rassismus in all seinen Ausprägungen scheint dieses Jahr extrem viel Platz auf meinen Leselisten einzunehmen. Insofern fand ich es interessant, hier zwei weiße Protagonisten zu sehen, die völlig überzeugt sind, nicht rassistisch zu sein, allerdings auf eine verquere Art genau das sind - und dabei den Splitter im Auge des Gegenübers sehen, nicht aber den Balken im eigenen Auge.

Allerdings wirken alle Figuren auf mich künstlich, einschließlich der Protagonistin und ihren Freunden, das kleine Mädchen, das sie betreut, wirkt auf mich absolut unglaublich für eine Dreijährige (und ich habe wirklich merkwürdige Dreijährige kennengelernt).

Insofern - spannender Ansatz, aber in der Ausführung für mich leider nicht wirklich gelungen.”; Ellemir. - In: LibraryThing, 25.03.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/review/155812303> [06.06.2023]

В социалната мрежа LibraryThing книгата „Such a Fun Age” е получила общо 157 коментара. От тях 156 са на английски език и 1 на немски език. Представени са най-новите 26 коментара на английски, както и коментара на немски и език.

1.2. Коментари в български онлайн книжарници

Книгата не е преведена на български език и не бяха открити мнения или коментари на български език.

Изводи за Фаза 1

Книгата „Such a Fun Age” има:

- Общо 111 проследени и отразени коментара в социалните мрежи
- 84 проследени коментара в социалната мрежа Goodreads, като 83 са на английски език и 1 на нидерландски език.
- Общо 157 комената в социалната мрежа LibraryThing, от които 156 са на английски и има един коментар на немски език. Представени са най-новите 27 на английски заедно с този на немски език.
- Не бе открита пряка обратна връзка с автора относно книгата.
- Не бяха открити коментари и отзиви в български онлайн книжарници.

На база проучването във фаза 1 книгата „Such a Fun Age” се е осъществила като медия, заради наличието на голямо количество обратна връзка.

Дијаграма 1. Брой извадени ревюта по години за книгата “Such a Fun Age” в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка на книгата

Във втора фаза ще бъде проучено в кои чуждестранни и български дигитални каталози фигурира книгата „Such a fun age: a novel”. Ще бъдат изследвани и виртуални книготърговски каталози, в които може да е отразена книгата.

2.1. Дигитални каталози на библиотеки в чужбина

OCLC Worldcat (Глобаен библиотечен каталог)

(<https://www.worldcat.org/title/1288105623>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, 2021. - 313 p.; 20 cm.

ISBN: 9780525541912

OCLC: 1288105623

Columbia University Libraries

(<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/14443231>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, [2019]. - 310 p.; 24 cm.

ISBN: 052554190X

ISBN: 9780525541905

Brooklyn Public Library

(<https://www.bklynlibrary.org/item?b=12239604>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, [2019]. - 310 p.; 24 cm.

ISBN: 052554190X

ISBN: 9780525541905

Beverly Hills Public Library

(<https://roxbury.beverlyhills.org/search/?Ysuch+a+fun+age&SORT=DZ/Ysuch+a+fun+age&SORT=DZ&extended=0&SUBKEY=such+a+fun+age>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: Random House Large Print, [2019]. - 389 p.; 24 cm.

ISBN: 9780593152379

ISBN: 0593152379

New York Public Library

(<https://nypl.na2.iiivega.com/search/card?id=53ede0af-f6f8-51d0-bb6d-ff992021fa8d&entityType=FormatGroup>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, [2019]. - 310 p.; 24 cm.

ISBN: 9780593152379

British Library

(https://explore.bl.uk/primo_library/libweb/action/display.do?tabs=moreTab&ct=display&fn=search&doc=BLL01019600957&indx=1&recIds=BLL01019600957&recIdxs=0&elementId=0&renderMode=poppedOut&displayMode)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: London: Bloomsbury Circus, 2020. - 310 p.; 23 cm.

ISBN: 9781526612144

ISBN: 9781526612151

Harvard University Library

(https://hollis.harvard.edu/primo-explore/fulldisplay?docid=01HVD_ALMA212325554170003941&context=L&vid=HV D2&lang=en_US&search_scope=default_scope&adaptor=)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: London: Bloomsbury Circus, 2020. - 310 p.; 24 cm.

ISBN: 9780525541905

ISBN: 052554190X

2.2. Световни виртуални каталози

AllBookstores.com

(<https://www.allbookstores.com/Such-Fun-Age-Reid-Kiley/9780525541912>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, 2021. - 336 p.

ISBN (10): 0525541918

ISBN (13): 9780525541912

Amazon.com

(https://www.amazon.com/Such-Fun-Age-Kiley-Reid/dp/0525541918/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2NM403APOYZ70&keywords=such+a+fun+a+ge+by+kiley+reid&qid=1685958233&prefix=such+a+%2Caps%2C219&sr=8-1)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, 2021. - 368 p.

ISBN (10): 0525541918

2.3. Виртуални книготърговски материали

ciela.com

(<https://www.ciela.com/such-a-fun-age.html>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a Fun Age: a novel. - In: New York: G.P. Putnam's Sons, 2020. - 320 p.

ISBN: 9781526612168

Knigomania.bg

(<https://knigomania.bg/such-a-fun-age.html>)

Reid, Kiley. Such a fun age: a novel. - Книгомания: Bloomsbury, 2020 - 320 с.

ISBN: 9781526612168

Изводи за Фаза 2

Книгата „Such a fun age“ на Кайли Рийд е представена чрез метаданни общо **11** пъти в:

- в най-малко **7** дигитални каталога на библиотеки в чужбина;
- **2** световни виртуални каталога;
- **2** български дигитални книготърговски каталога.

Резултатите от Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка показват, че книгата „Such a fun age“ на Кайли Рийд се е осъществила като медия предимно в чужбина. Книгата не се среща в български библиотеки, а само като виртуални книготърговски материали без превод.

Поради липсата на информация данните не могат да бъдат проследени по години, затова ще бъдат визуализирани според видовете каталози, в които е отразена книгата.

Диаграма 2. Номинална (формална) обработка на книгата “Such a Fun Age” в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието

3.1. Анотации

Reid, Kiley. Such a fun age: a novel. - In: Goodreads, 31.12.2019. Available from: https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/26247008-truly-madly-guilty?from_search=true&from_srp=true&qid=MvMI8Bkd73&rank=1 [05.06.2023]

Рид, Кайли. Такой забавный возраст. - In: LiveLib, 2022. Available from: <https://www.livelib.ru/book/1003031045-vernye-bezumnye-vinovnye-liana-moriarti> [05.06.2023]

„Such a Fun Age“ von Kiley Reid - auf Deutsch. - In: Buchstapelweise, 16.07.2021. Available from: <https://buchstapelweise.com/2021/08/16/such-a-fun-age-von-kiley-reid-auf-deutsch> [05.06.2023]

Reid, Kiley. Los años mejores. - In: Qué libro leo, [2008-2023]. Available from: <https://quelibroleo.com/los-mejores-anos#:~:text=> [05.06.2023]

3.2. Резюме, реферат и съкратени версии

Such a fun age: The Bibliofile Book Reviews. - In: The Bibliofile Book Reviews & etc, 31.12.2019. Available from: <https://the-bibliofile.com/such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Reid, Kiley. Such a fun age: a novel. - In: Book Browse, [1997-2023]. Available from: https://www.bookbrowse.com/bb_briefs/detail/index.cfm/ezine_preview_number/14730/such-a-fun-age [05.06.2023]

Reid, Kiley. Such a fun age: a novel. - In: Super Summary, [2023]. Available from: <https://www.supersummary.com/such-a-fun-age/summary> [05.06.2023]

Masad, Ilana. 'Such A Fun Age' Is A Complex, Layered Page-Turner. - In: NPR, 28.12.2019. Available from: <https://www.npr.org/2019/12/28/791747689/such-a-fun-age-is-a-complex-layered-page-turner> [05.06.2023]

Book Club: "Such a Fun Age" by Kiley Reid. - In: She's Full of Lit, [2020]. Available from: <https://www.shesfulloflit.com/blog/book-club-such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

Reid, Kiley. Los años mejores. - In: Qué libro leo, [2008-2023]. Available from: <https://quelibroleo.com/los-mejores-anos#:~:text=> [05.06.2023]

Рид, Кайли. Такой забавный возраст. - In: Литрес, 2021. Available from: <https://www.litres.ru/book/kayli-rid/takoy-zabavnyy-vozrast-67720016> [05.06.2023]

„Such a Fun Age“ von Kiley Reid - auf Deutsch. - In: Buchstapelweise, 16.07.2021. Available from: <https://buchstapelweise.com/2021/08/16/such-a-fun-age-von-kiley-reid-auf-deutsch> [05.06.2023]

Изводи за Фаза 3

Книгата на Кайли Рийд има една анотация, написана на английски език, която е преведена на 3 езика - немски, руски и испански.

Резюмета или съкратени версии на творбата на Кайли Рийд се срещат в много сайтове на различни езици, представени от погледа на читатели и експерти. Резюметата се достъпни на няколко езика.

Няма резултати за анонси, свързани с книгата, като причина за това е липсата на екранизации, както и ниската популярност.

Дијаграма 3. Редукция на съдържанието на книгата „Such a Fun Age“ в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата

Във Фаза 4 ще бъдат търсени преводи, различни формати на книгата и цитирания на книгата „Such a fun age“ от Кайли Рийд.

4.1. Преводи

Книгата „Such a fun age“ е преведена на три езика - испански, немски и руски.

- Reid, Kiley. Los mejores años. - Suma de Letras, 2021.
- Reid, Kiley. Such a fun age. - Ullstein Hardcover, 2021.
- Рид, Кайли. Такой забавный возраст. - Фантом Пресс, 2022.

4.2 Цитиране

Цитати или откъси от книгата „Such a fun age“ са поместени в следните онлайн източници:

Anderson, Hephzibah. Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid - charming, authentic, entertaining. - In: The Guardian, 07.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/jan/07/such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid-review> [05.06.2023]

Book Club: "Such a Fun Age" by Kiley Reid. - In: She's Full of Lit, 19.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.shesfulloflit.com/blog/book-club-such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

Grady, Constance. The smart political argument behind the satire Such a Fun Age. - In: Vox, 19.11.2021. Available from: <https://www.vox.com/culture/22790112/such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

[Hundred] 100 Books About Siblings That You May Enjoy. - In: Motivational Wizard, 17.05.2023. Available from: <https://motivationalwizard.com/books-about-siblings> [05.06.2023]

Kovan, Brianna. Such a Fun Age Author Kiley Reid Wants to Make You Cringe. - In: Elle, 28.12.2019. Available from: <https://www.elle.com/culture/books/a30296948/kiley-reid-such-a-fun-age-interview> [05.06.2023]

Lin, Jennifer. Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid - Summary and Review. - In: The Bibliofile, 21.07.2020. Available from: <https://the-bibliofile.com/such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Los mejores años (Reseña). - In: BlogLiterario, 19.04.2021. Available from: <https://blogliterario.com/los-mejores-anos-resena> [05.06.2023]

Los mejores años. - In: Algunos Libros Buenos, 08.03.2021. Available from: <https://algunoslibrosbuenos.com/los-mejores-anos> [05.06.2023]

Louisa. 27 Engaging Such a Fun Age Book Club Questions. - In: Epic Book Society, 29.09.2022. Available from: <https://epicbooksociety.com/such-a-fun-age-book-club-questions> [05.06.2023]

Shaffi, Sarah. Such A Fun Age: why everyone is talking about Kiley Reid's debut novel. - In: Stylist, 2019. Available from: <https://www.stylist.co.uk/books/such-a-fun-age-book-kiley-reid-interview-debut-novel-white-privilege-racism-america/349858> [05.06.2023]

Such a Fun Age Quotes. - In: Good Reads, [2023]. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/work/quotes/63995465-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Such a Fun Age Themes. - In: Super Summary, [2023]. Available from: <https://www.supersummary.com/such-a-fun-age/themes> [05.06.2023]

Weidermann, Volker. Wovor liberale Weiße Angst haben. - In: Der Spiegel, 04.06.2021. Available from: <https://www.spiegel.de/kultur/literatur/such-a-fun-age-von-kiley-reid-wovor-liberale-weisse-angst-haben-a-adceff6f-0002-0001-0000-000177779200> [05.06.2023]

Изводи за Фаза 4

Търсачката Google намира около 108 000 резултата, свързани с цитиране на книгата на Кайли Рийд “Such a Fun Age”. Визуализираните резултати предоставят информация предимно за ревьюта, резюмета или анотации на книгата. Докато онлайн източниците, които използват отделни извадки на откъси от книгата, са значително по-малко. Голяма част от резултатите насочват читателя към онлайн книжарници, чрез може да се закупи книгата. Резултатите от Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) доказват, че “Such a Fun Age” се е осъществила като медия, тъй като съществуват преводи на три езика.

Диаграма 4. Репродукции на книгата “Such a Fun Age” в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика

Във Фаза 5 ще бъдат търсени отзиви и рецензии в медиите и публикуваните ревюта (читателски прегледи) за книгата “Such a fun age” на Кайли Рийд.

5.1. Отзиви и рецензии в медиите

Aviles, Gwen. Kiley Reid's 'Such a Fun Age' probes the insidious forms of racism. - In: NBC News, 04.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.nbcnews.com/pop-culture/books/kiley-reid-s-such-fun-age-probes-insidious-forms-racism-n1110021> [05.06.2023]

Bingham, Chelsea. Such a Fun Age. - In: Harvard Review, 04.08.2020. Available from: <https://www.harvardreview.org/book-review/such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Christensen, Lauren. When It Comes to Race, How Progressive Are the Progressives? - In: The New York Times, 31.12.2019. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/12/31/books/review/such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid.html> [05.06.2023]

Collins, Sara. Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid review - an essential new talent. - In: The Guardian, 02.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/jan/02/such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid-review-white-liberals-black-people> [05.06.2023]

Glover, Richard. Such a fun age: This is when you're at your comedic peak. - In: Sydney Morning Herald, 10.02.2023. Available from: <https://www.smh.com.au/lifestyle/life-and-relationships/such-a-fun-age-this-is-when-you-re-at-your-comedic-peak-20230207-p5cijz.html> [05.06.2023]

Hart, Michelle. Kiley Reid's Juicy Debut Such a Fun Age Skewers "Woke" White Women. - In: Oprah Daily, 15.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.oprahdaily.com/entertainment/books/a30460279/kiley-reid-such-a-fun-age-review> [05.06.2023]

Hayes, Stephanie. Such a Fun Age Satirizes the White Pursuit of Wokeness. - In: The Atlantic, 08.01.2020. Available from:

<https://www.theatlantic.com/entertainment/archive/2020/01/review-such-fun-age-kiley-reid/604552> [05.06.2023]

Kauffman, Susan. Bestselling 'Such a Fun Age' selected for class of 2025 summer reading. - In: Duke today, 11.05.2021. Available from: <https://today.duke.edu/2021/05/bestselling-such-fun-age-selected-class-2025-summer-reading> [05.06.2023]

Nebbe, Charity; Harrop, Katelyn; Starr, Monica. Kiley Reid On Class, Race and Intentions In “Such A Fun Age”. - In: Iowa Public Radio, 18.03.2021. Available from: <https://www.iowapublicradio.org/arts-life/2021-03-18/kiley-reid-on-class-race-and-intentions-in-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Patrick, Bethanie. In ‘Such a Fun Age,’ Philly’s Kiley Reid takes aim at race and class in America | Book review. - In: The Philadelphia Inquirer, 15.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.inquirer.com/arts/books/such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid-book-review-20200115.html> [05.06.2023]

Patrick, Bethanne. In ‘Such a Fun Age,’ Kiley Reid takes aim at race and class in America. - In: Washington Post, 06.01.2020. Available from: https://www.washingtonpost.com/entertainment/books/in-such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid-takes-aim-at-race-and-class-in-america/2020/01/06/a51ff034-2d8e-11ea-bcb3-ac6482c4a92f_story.html [05.06.2023]

Thomas-Kennedy, Jackie. Review: 'Such a Fun Age,' by Kiley Reid. - In: StarTribune, 27.12.2019. Available from: <https://www.startribune.com/review-such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid/56651090> [05.06.2023]

Wiegandt, Kai. Frauen, die sich Gehör verschaffen. - In: Die Zeit, 22.05.2023. Available from: https://www.zeit.de/2021/21/such-a-fun-age-kiley-reid-roman-rassismus-klassismus-usa?utm_referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F [05.06.2023]

5.2. Публикувани ревюта (читателски прегледи)

Book review - “Such a Fun Age” by Kiley Reid. - In: Julia’s books, 28.03.2021. Available from: <https://julias-books.com/2021/03/28/book-review-such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

Book Review: Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid. - In: Chapters of May, 07.02.2020. Available from: <https://chaptersofmay.com/such-a-fun-age-review> [05.06.2023]

Book Review: Such a Fun Age. - In: Chonky Books, 28.02.2023. Available from: <https://chonkybooksreview.com/2023/02/28/book-review-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Brooks, Nicola. Wokeness and its Failures in Kiley Reid’s Such a Fun Age. - In: American Literature and Culture at Queen’s, 02.11.2022. Available from: <https://blogs.qub.ac.uk/americanists/2022/11/02/wokeness-and-its-failures-in-kiley-reids-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Is Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid Worth the Hype? Definitely. Read a Review Here. - In: Better Reading, 07.09.2020. Available from: <https://www.betterreading.com.au/review/is-such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid-worth-the-hype-definitely-read-a-review-here> [05.06.2023]

Lin, Jennifer. Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid - Summary and Review. - In: The Bibliolife, 21.07.2020. Available from: <https://the-bibliofile.com/such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Masa, Ilana. 'Such A Fun Age' is a Complex, Layered Page-Turner. - In: KQED, 06.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.kqed.org/arts/13872459/such-a-fun-age-is-a-complex-layered-page-turner> [05.06.2023]

My Thoughts On: Such a Fun Age by Kiley Reid. - In: Books For The Living, 08.02.2021. Available from: <https://booksfortheiving.wordpress.com/2021/02/08/such-a-fun-age-by-kiley-reid-review> [05.06.2023]

Questions About Such a Fun Age. - In: Goodreads, [2023]. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/book/43923951/questions> [05.06.2023]

Such a Fun Age von Kiley Reid - auf Deutsch. - In: Buchstapelweise, 16.08.2021. Available from: <https://buchstapelweise.com/2021/08/16/such-a-fun-age-von-kiley-reid-auf-deutsch> [05.06.2023]

5.3. Интервюта за книгата

Akhtar, Jabeen. How “Such a Fun Age” Came to Be: An Interview with Kiley Reid. - In: Los Angeles Review of Books, 02.01.2021. Available from: <https://lareviewofbooks.org/article/how-such-a-fun-age-came-to-be-an-interview-with-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

Armitstead, Claire. Kiley Reid: 'The premise that literary fiction has to be a drag is so silly'. - In: The Guardian, 27.12.2020. Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/dec/27/kiley-reid-interview-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Author Chat w/ Kiley Reid, Such A Fun Age. - In: SBG Book Club, 30.07.2020. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RTh0aK8XCh4> [05.06.2023]

Bhasin, Simar. Interview: Kiley Reid, author of Such a Fun Age. - In: Hindustan Times, 04.09.2020. Available from: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/books/new-thoughts-on-big-broken-systems/story-lzFe93yAl6tMKpgtGBkvfP.html> [05.06.2023]

Fadel Leila. Kiley Reid On 'Such A Fun Age'. - In: NPR, 28.12.2019. Available from: <https://www.npr.org/2019/12/28/792022308/kiley-reid-on-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Kiley Reid - Race, Class and Awkwardness in "Such a Fun Age". - In: The Daily Show, 26.03.2020. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UTP8jVb1uAY> [05.06.2023]

Lip, Cassandra. Breaking In: An Interview With Such a Fun Age Author Kiley Reid. - In: Writer's Digest, 04.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.writersdigest.com/getting-published/breaking-in-an-interview-with-such-a-fun-age-author-kiley-reid> [05.06.2023]

Rankin, Seija. Kiley Reid reflects on the success of Such a Fun Age: 'You cannot solve racism through consumption'. - In: Entertainment Weekly, 19.04.2021. Available from: <https://ew.com/books/kiley-reid-such-a-fun-age-interview> [05.06.2023]

Such a Fun Age | Kiley Reid in Conversation with Hannah MacInnes. - In: How To Academy Mindset, 13.03.2020. Available from: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JD4DYY6_YMQ [05.06.2023]

West, Abby. Kiley Reid's 'Such A Fun Age' Is More Than Just Fun. - In: Audible Blog, 23.01.2020. Available from: <https://www.audible.com/blog/kiley-reids-such-a-fun-age-is-more-than-just-fun> [05.06.2023]

Изводи за Фаза 5

В интернет има много информация за книгата „Such a Fun Age“. Открити са много публикувани ревюта, читателски прегледи и 9 интервюта с автора на книгата - Кайли Рийд. При проучване на Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика на изданието за „Such a Fun Age“ е установено, че най-широк обществен отклик има през 2020 г. - 34% от всички резултати към днешна дата. Въпреки това

продължава да се говори за книгата и да се публикуват рецензии. Резултатите за периода 2019 - 2023 г. са онагледени чрез диаграма.

След проучване на симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка се доказва, че книгата “Such a Fun Age” се е осъществила като медия.

Диаграма 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика на книгата “Such a Fun Age” в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Фаза 6. Експертна (научна) критика

Във Фаза 6 ще бъде търсена научна критика за книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кайли Рийд и наградите, които книгата е спечелила в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

6.1. Професионални награди

1. Победител в афро-американската литературна награда. (2020 г.)

2. Спечелена награда Goodreads Choice за най-добър дебютен роман (2020 г.)

6.2. Изследвания и интерпретации

Изследванията и интерпретациите на книгата на Кили Рийд са събрани в книги - резюмета, включват анотации и изследвания. Представени са във фаза 3.

Изводи за Фаза 6

Книгата получава две награди през 2020 г., съответно победител в афро-американската литературна награда и награда Goodreads Choice за най-добър дебютен роман, но е финалист за още много различни и големи награди. Книгата събира доста голям интерес и по тази причина има доста резюмета и анализи по оригинала. Научната критика доказва, че книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кили Рийд се е осъществила като медия.

Фаза 7. Медиаморфози

Във Фаза 7 ще бъдат търсени медиаморфози на книгата “Such a Fun Age” на Кили Рийд в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

7.1. Екранизация

През август 2020 г. е обявено, че Hillman Grad Productions и Sight Unseen Pictured на Lena Waithe са придобили филмовите и телевизионни права върху „Such a Fun Age“. Тогавашната адаптация е била в начален етап, актьорският състав все още не е бил ясен, нямало е дата на излъчване, както и трейлъър. Тази екранизация все още не е осъществена, няма информация за сценаристите, актьорите и режисьора.

Новини за екранизацията:

1. Such A Fun Age Movie: What We Know. - In: The Bibliofile, 01.08.2020. Available from: <https://the-bibliofile.com/such-a-fun-age-movie-release-cast-trailer-film> [05.06.2023]
2. From Page to Screen: Kiley Reid’s Debut Novel SUCH A FUN AGE. - In: Penguin Random House. Available from: <https://global.penguinrandomhouse.com/announcements/from-page-to-screen-kiley-reids-debut-novel-such-a-fun-age> [05.06.2023]

Изводи за Фаза 7

По книгата няма направени театрална постановка, изложба или друга практика, появила се в следствие на прочита на книгата. Предвидената екранизация все още не е осъществена. Няма и дискусия по книгата, която да се е провела. Медиаморфози доказват, че книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кайли Рийд се е осъществила като медия, поради интереса към нея от страна на продуценти за нейното екранизиране, въпреки че все още не е.

Фаза 8. Историзация

Във Фаза 8 ще бъдат търсени класации, в които е включена книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кили Рийд в периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

8.1 Класации на книгата

За 2020 г. книгата „Such a Fun Age” е в класациите: Goodreads номиниран за най-добра фантастика, победител за най-добър дебютен роман, както и в класациите за награда Букър.

Изводи за Фаза 8

В периода 2019 - юни 2023 г. книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кайли Рийд е включена в 3 класации - през 2020 г.

Рекапитулация на резултатите

Общият брой на всички открити резултати от информационния мониторинг във всяка от осемте фази на информационен резонанс на книгата „Such a fun age“ на Кайли Рийд е визуализиран в диаграма.

Фаза 1. Симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка - общо 166 резултата (67%).

Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка показва, че книгата е отразена 11 пъти (4%) с метаданни в дигитални каталози на библиотеки и онлайн книготърговски каталози.

Във Фаза 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието информационния резонанс под формата на анотации и новини за книгата е осъществена 12 пъти (5%).

Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата отразява 16 резултата (7%) - книгата е преведена на 3 езика и е цитирана в 13 онлайн източника. Не са намерени различни издания.

Във Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика има общо 33 резултата (13%) - 13 отзива в медиите, 10 ревята (читателски прегледи) и 10 интервюта с автора. Книгата не е отразена в списъци с препоръчителни библиографии.

Във Фаза 6. Експертна (научна) критика, професионални награди; изследвания и интерпретации за информационен резонанс на книгата има общо 6 резултата (2%), от които 2 професионални награди и 4 публикации, в които книгата е обект на научна критика.

Във Фаза 7. Медиаморфози са отрити 2 резултата (1%). Има неуспешен опит за екранизация на книгата.

Фаза 8. Историзация отразява 3 резултата (1%) - участието на книгата в годишни класации.

Диаграма 6. Информационен резонанс на книгата “Such a Fun Age” по фази за периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

В Диаграма 7 са представени резултатите от осемте фази за информационен резонанс на книгата “Such a Fun Age” на ИМЕТО, разделени по години.

Диаграма 7. Информационен резонанс на книгата “Such a Fun Age” по години за периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

Изданието е реализирано най-добре през 2019 г. - 74 резултата. На второ място е 2021 г. с 31 резултата, трето място - 2020 - 26 резултата, 2022 г. на четвърто - 24 резултата и 2023 г. на пето - 18 резултата.

В Диаграма 8 се проследява съвкупността от всички събрани данни от информационния резонанс на книгата “Such a Fun Age” на ИМЕТО, обособени по фази и години.

Диаграма 8. Информационен резонанс на книгата “Such a fun age” по фази и години за периода 2019 - юни 2023 г.

За пет години най-високи стойности в информационния резонанс на книгата се наблюдават във Фаза 1 през 2019 г. и 2022 г. и Фаза 5 през 2020 г. Във Фаза 7 има липса на информационен резонанс, тъй като книгата не е екранизирана. През 2022 г. и 2023 г. има липса на такъв интерес към книгата и съответно спад в резултатите.

Финален извод

Резултатите от проведеното проучване за периода 2019 - юни 2023 г. доказват успешното комуникиране на книгата „Such a Fun Age“ на Кайли Рийд и осъществяването ѝ като медия. Създадена е ефективна комуникация между автора и читателите и е провокирана бърза и мащабна обратна връзка.

Във фаза 1, са проследени 111 коментара в социалните мрежи, 84 в социалната мрежа Goodreads, както и общо 157 коментара в LibraryThing

съответно на различни езици. За съжаление не бяха открити отзиви от български онлайн книжарници. Книгата е отразена 11 пъти с метаданни в дигитални каталози на библиотеки и онлайн книготърговски каталози. Книгата на Кайли Рийд има една анотация и различни резюмета на различни езици. Най-голям успех има във фаза 4, където се откриват най-много резултати и е представена информация, че книгата съществува на три езика. Във фаза 5 „Текуща (оперативна) критика” се открива, че има много информация за книгата и е установено, че най-широк обществен отклик има през 2020 г. Книгата получава две награди през същата година, но събира голям интерес и по тази причина има издадени книги, които включват резюмета и анализи по оригинала. По нея няма направени театрални постановки, екранизации, изложби или други практики, появили се в следствие на прочита на книгата. Въпреки това, книгата е включена в 3 класации през 2020 г.